

FINANCIAL LITERACY AS CORRELATES TO TEACHERS' PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT: BASIS TO A PROPOSED FISCAL SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the financial literacy as correlates to Teachers' Personal and Professional development: Basis to a proposed fiscal sustainability plan. The descriptive correlated type of research method was used in the study. The 100 respondents are all elementary teachers in Tiaong II District, Division of Quezon. The main instrument used in gathering data was the self-made and adopted survey questionnaire checklist using the Likert scale. The statistical treatments used are mean, frequency distribution, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The data revealed that perceived financial literacy as to of financial knowledge is significantly related to the personal and professional development in terms of financial stability, financial wellness, financial capability, financial investment, financial inclusion and retirement plan. Financial behavior is significantly related to the personal and professional development as to financial stability, financial wellness, financial capability, financial investment, financial inclusion and retirement plan. Financial attitudes are significantly related to the personal and professional development as to financial stability, financial wellness, financial capability, financial investment, financial inclusion and retirement plan. Financial management in terms of savings, debt and expenses are all significantly related to the personal and professional development as to financial stability, financial wellness, financial capability, financial investment, financial inclusion and retirement plan. Furthermore the perceived financial literacy in terms of financial knowledge is significantly related to the fiscal sustainability as to available resources, financial controls and expenditures. Therefore the hypothesis was not sustained.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Personal and Professional Development, Fiscal Sustainability